

WISE AI Testbed Evaluation Framework - Condensed

**Nariman Moustafa
Christopher Klune
Syed Mustafa Hassan
Jennie Lester**

April 2026

<https://doi.org/10.53832/opendeved.1206>

© 2026, Open Development & Education. This report is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

About this document

Recommended citation

Moustafa, N., Klune, C., Hassan, S. M., & Lester, J. (2026). WISE AI Testbed Evaluation Framework - Full consolidated version [Report]. Open Development & Education. <https://doi.org/10.53832/opendeved.1207>

Table of Contents

0. Context & Strategic Fit.....	4
1. Domain: Evidence of Effectiveness & Support.....	4
2. Domain: Usability, Infrastructure & Training.....	4
3. Domain: Pedagogical Effectiveness & Workflow.....	5
4. Domain: Equity and Accessibility.....	6
5. Domain: Ethics, Data Privacy and Security.....	7
6. Domain: Cost & Sustainability.....	8

0. Context & Strategic Fit

Focus: Provides necessary context before scoring begins.

0.1 Tool Purpose & Development:

- **Metric:** Tool Purpose (e.g., Personalized learning, Assessment, Lesson planning).
- **Metric:** Development Stage (Prototype vs. Scaling).

1. Domain: Evidence of Effectiveness & Support

Focus: Does the tool have a track record, and will the provider support us?

1.1 Existing Evidence & Impact:

- **Metric:** Existence of evidence (No evidence vs. multiple sources).
- **Metric:** Evidence sources (Internal/supplier vs. external/academic research).
- **Metric:** Impact on Diverse Learners (Overall averages vs. strong disaggregated data).
- **Metric:** Tool tested with diverse populations (No testing vs. broad/diverse backgrounds).

1.2 Provider Support & Capacity:

- **Metric:** Free trial availability (No vs. yes).
- **Metric:** Local support channels (No local support vs. ongoing local support).
- **Metric:** Provider responsiveness (Adhoc vs. strong mechanisms for feedback).

2. Domain: Usability, Infrastructure & Training

Focus: Can we technically run it, and can teachers learn it?

2.1 Technical Interoperability & Infrastructure:

- **Metric:** Integration (Demanding set-up vs. seamless LMS/SSO integration).
- **Metric:** Device compatibility (Requires new hardware vs. fully compatible with existing devices).
- **Metric:** Offline capabilities (Cannot function offline vs. fully functional offline).

2.2 User Experience (UX):

- **Metric:** Intuition (Hard to navigate vs. self-learn).
- **Metric:** Aesthetics & Functionality (Cluttered/unresponsive vs. clear, age-appropriate, and responsive).

2.3 Training & Professional Development (Quality + Cost):

- **Metric:** Training Availability (None available vs. available for all features).
- **Metric:** Training Materials Ease of Use (Difficult/non-engaging vs. highly engaging/easy to use).
- **Metric:** Training Time (Unclear/infeasible vs. clear and feasible).
- **Metric:** PD Format (No support vs. regional/global Community of Practice).
- **Metric:** Teacher Training Cost (High extra cost vs. openly accessible/included).

3. Domain: Pedagogical Effectiveness & Workflow

Focus: Does it improve teaching/learning, and is the workflow manageable?

3.1 Alignment & Transformation:

- **Metric:** Alignment with educational philosophy (Little alignment vs. strong alignment).
- **Metric:** Curricular alignment per subject (0-29% vs. 81-100% complete alignment).
- **Metric:** Matching learning goals (Non-existing vs. primary instructional goals).
- **Metric:** Task Transformation - SAMR (Substitution vs. Redefinition of tasks).
- **Metric:** Dedicated educational team (None vs. experienced team utilizing sound theory).

3.2 Personalization & Differentiation Workflow:

- **Metric:** Personalised pathways (Static sequence vs. comprehensive/adaptive teacher-orchestrated paths).
- **Metric:** Differentiated content, scaffolds, and modalities (Minimal/cosmetic vs. strong variation).
- **Metric:** Learner model and diagnosis (Limited single data point vs. advanced ongoing profile).

- **Metric:** Ease of use for differentiation (Cumbersome vs. streamlined to reduce workload).
- **Metric:** Fairness of Personalisation (Locks into "low" tracks vs. fairness by design/transparency).

3.3 Home–School Use to Support Personalisation:

- **Metric:** Home-school connection (No connection vs. strong data integration into classroom planning).

3.4 Agency & Feedback:

- **Metric:** Teacher Empowerment (Undermines role vs. amplifies/enhances teacher agency).
- **Metric:** Learner Autonomy (Over-relies on automation vs. strong learner voice/choice).
- **Metric:** Feedback Quality (Quality issues vs. highly responsive/pedagogically sound).
- **Metric:** Impact on existing school processes (Disruptive vs. seamlessly aligns/enhances).
- **Metric:** Effect on teaching and learner relationships (Creates distance vs. enhances relational pedagogies).
- **Metric:** Effect on accountability mechanisms (Reduces transparency vs. strengthens accountability).

4. Domain: Equity and Accessibility

Focus: Can we see what is happening, and is it inclusive for all learners?

4.1 Actionable Analytics:

- **Metric:** Data collection ability (Generic usage vs. specific/disaggregated learning events).
- **Metric:** Transparency/Explainability (Opaque vs. transparent and co-designed with learners).
- **Metric:** Equity-aware analytics (Whole-class averages vs. easy filtering with guided actions).
- **Metric:** Suggestions to teachers & Override capability (No suggestions vs. teacher inputs integrated).

- **Metric:** Suggestions to parents (None vs. available with engagement opportunities).

4.2 Cultural & Linguistic Responsiveness:

- **Metric:** Arabic Support (No support vs. Arabic-first with Gulf variants).
- **Metric:** Cultural Adaptability (Not responsive vs. homegrown for the context).

4.3 Accessibility:

- **Metric:** Digital accessibility (Inaccessible vs. comprehensively accessible for disabilities).

5. Domain: Ethics, Data Privacy and Security

Focus: Is it safe, fair, and compliant?

5.1 Bias Mitigation & Ethical Design:

- **Metric:** Stakeholder consultation (No involvement vs. co-designed with educators/students).
- **Metric:** Developer ethics training (No training vs. formally trained in ethics/child rights).
- **Metric:** Bias mitigation (No mitigation vs. consistently tested for race/gender/culture).

5.2 Transparency & Compliance:

- **Metric:** Supplier transparency on data storage and usage (Vague vs. publicly available/accessible).
- **Metric:** Legitimacy of data use and rationale (Unjustified vs. clearly tied to educational outcomes).
- **Metric:** Legal and policy alignment (Non-compliant vs. complies fully with national/school policies).

5.3 Data Privacy & Sovereignty:

- **Metric:** Data hosting location (Outside Qatar vs. homegrown/hosted in Qatar by default).
- **Metric:** Safe zones (Continuous monitoring vs. clearly designated assessment-free spaces).

6. Domain: Cost & Sustainability

Focus: Is it financially viable?

6.1 Total Cost of Ownership (TCO):

- **Metric:** Overall affordability (High cost/unclear benefits vs. transparent/justified benefits).
- **Metric:** Licensing clarity (Complex/frequent renewals vs. flexible/school-friendly options).
- **Metric:** Maintenance (Costly/school responsible vs. proactive support included).